

Collatz on more primes3

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Let $C_3(t)$ be the Collatz function

$$C_3(t) = (3t + 1)/2 \quad \text{for } t \text{ odd}$$

and $h(t)$ the halving function

$$H(t) = t/2 \quad \text{for } t \text{ even}$$

For any odd prime p , Collatz iteration (as appropriate)

$$C_3(H(C_3(H(\dots(p))))))$$

ends in a prime, sometimes very quickly; thus a variant of the famous conjecture.

For example, let $p = 23$; Collatz iteration yields the sequence

23, 35, 53, 80, 40, 20, 10, **5**

Even the considerably larger prime 25,612,864,321,621 reaches a prime in 21 passes:

25,612,864,321,621; 38,419,296,482,432; 19,209,648,241,216; 9,604,824,120,608;
4,802,412,060,304; 2,401,206,030,152; 1,200,603,015,076; 600,301,507,538;
300,150,753,769; 450,226,130,654; 225,113,065,327; 337,669,597,991;
506,504,396,987; 759,756,595,481; 1,139,634,893,222; 569,817,446,611;
854,726,169,917; 1,282,089,254,876; 641,044,627,438; 320,522,313,719;
480,783,470,579; **721,175,205,869**

The image below charts prime endpoints results; in the top tier, the star black line traces the starting primes, the stop primes in circled stars; the lower tier shows iteration counts to stops.

Questions and Observations.

- 1) 144 of the 200 stop primes obtained through iteration were unique; of these, only 118 matched starters. So, is Collatz eventually closed on primes?
- 2) At most 18 iterations were required to reach a prime here, for starter 599; parsimonious compared to conventional integer starters.
- 3) Even the large prime listed at the outset needed only 21 iterations to stop.
- 4) 41 primes were reached after just one pass, forming Collatz prime-pairs $(p, C_3(p))$ - or just Collatz primes - tabled below; starters in white, stops in red. There were also five pairs of consecutive pairs, highlighted in yellow.

3	7	11	19	31	47	59	67	71	131	151	167	179	211	239	307	311	347	431	439
5	11	17	29	47	71	89	101	107	197	227	251	269	317	359	461	467	521	647	659

467	479	547	571	587	607	619	631	647	727	739	787	811	839	859	907	911	967	991	1039	1091
701	719	821	857	881	911	929	947	971	1091	1109	1181	1217	1259	1289	1361	1367	1451	1487	1559	1637

The number of Collatz primes seems to follow closely the prime counter, since $200/\log(200) \approx 38$.

- 5) Prime hopping for conventional convergence:
Three easy examples

7 -> 11 -> 17 -> 13 -> 5 -> **2**
19 -> 29 -> 11 -> 17 -> 13 -> 5 -> **2**
59 -> 89 -> 67 -> 101 -> 19 -> 29 -> 11 -> 17 -> 13 -> 5 -> **2**

The next, more circuitous, still reached the end in 22 steps:

31 -> 47 -> 71 -> 107 -> 137 -> 103 -> 233 -> 263 -> 593 -> 167 -> 251 -> 283 -> 479 -> 719 -> 1619 -> 911 -> 1367 -> 577 -> 433 -> 61 -> 23 -> 5 -> **2**

By comparison, conventional iteration starting at **31** reached the end about three times slower, in 67 steps; see image below.

Now, the cumulative sum of this Collatz sequence scaled by its maximum value (see below)

looks suspiciously like a probability distribution function (pdf); so, is the famous conjecture really about distributional convergence?

- 6) The known non-prime 25,612,864,321,621 reached the known prime 160,261,156,859 in (again) 21 passes; is Collatz iteration useful for prime hunting?
- 7) Is the famous conjecture any easier to prove for primes? Convergence certainly seems much faster when prime-hopping.
- 8) Does the prime counter estimate apply to Collatz primes in the large?

Let

$$\pi(x) = \#\{\text{primes } p: 2 < p \leq x\}$$

be the usual prime counter starting at 3, and

$$\sigma(x) = \#\{\text{Collatz primes } p: 2 < p \leq x\}$$

Incremental testing in OCTAVE suggests the Collatz Primes Conjecture:

$$\sigma(x) \rightarrow \pi(x)/2\log_{10}(\pi(x)) \quad \text{for sufficiently large } x$$

Numerical estimation in up to 10 million (664,578 odd primes) supports this estimate; percentage errors fell well below 1% after some 13,000 start primes (see next image and supporting spreadsheet on p. 4).

General reference: Wikipedia article on the Collatz Conjecture.

n	odd $\pi(n)$	$C_3(\pi)$	Estimate	%Error
500	94	24	24	0.75
1000	167	41	38	8.37
1500	238	49	50	2.19
2000	302	65	61	6.33
2500	366	74	71	3.53
3000	429	83	81	1.83
3500	488	93	91	2.41
4000	549	102	100	1.77
5000	668	119	118	0.64
6000	782	137	135	1.35
7000	899	153	152	0.54
8000	1006	167	168	0.31
9000	1116	185	183	1.03
10000	1228	203	199	2.09
15000	1753	273	270	1.02
20000	2261	342	337	1.45
30000	3244	461	462	0.21
40000	4202	592	580	2.06
45000	4674	645	637	1.27
50000	5132	708	692	2.32
60000	6056	815	801	1.77
70000	6934	912	903	1.03
80000	7836	1014	1006	0.78
90000	8712	1119	1106	1.20
95000	9156	1175	1156	1.65
96000	9251	1184	1166	1.50
97000	9335	1193	1176	1.45
98000	9417	1204	1185	1.59
99000	9504	1216	1195	1.76
99500	9546	1220	1199	1.70
100000	9591	1227	1204	1.85
130000	12158	1506	1488	1.18
150000	13847	1681	1672	0.55
200000	17983	2096	2113	0.82
300000	25996	2946	2946	0.00
400000	33859	3760	3737	0.60
500000	41537	4517	4497	0.45
1000000	78497	7988	8018	0.38
2000000	148932	14290	14395	0.74
3000000	216815	20336	20316	0.10
4000000	283145	26064	25967	0.37
5000000	348512	31532	31442	0.29
6000000	412848	36826	36758	0.19
7000000	476647	41966	41972	0.01
8000000	539776	47062	47083	0.04
9000000	602488	52097	52119	0.04
10000000	664578	57032	57069	0.07